

Effect of Compaction on Kinetics of Thermal Dehydration of Silicic Acid and Aluminium Hydroxide Hydrogels

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The dehydration kinetics have been studied by TG method. The effect of compaction could not contribute to major changes in the hydrogel structures and also in the orientation of water molecules. Effect of increase of pressure was inversely affecting the validity of first order kinetics. The escape of loosely bound water was a low-energy process.

WATER is an integral part of the gel structure. Various physico-chemical properties of the hydrogels depend on the magnitude and orientation of water molecules. Thus water is thought to be the solely decomposition product of hydrous oxides. This can either be formed uniformly throughout the crystal by combination of hydroxyl group with the proton of an adjacent group (homogeneous mechanism) or by a counter migration of protons and metal ions to region which subsequently forms water and oxide, respectively (inhomogeneous mechanism).

Gelatinous aluminium hydroxide materials are of great interest because of their industrial importance in preparing sorbents and catalysts. Various types of gels were investigated¹⁻³, in most cases precipitated from alum or aluminium sulfate solution by ammonia at a temperature below 60°. Alumina gels were prepared⁴ at pH 3.5 to 7.0. Kendykin⁵ stated that primary amorphous particles are oval, 0.01 to 0.05 micron in diameter, in agreement with the size as determined from specific surface measurements.

Jingensons and Straumanis⁶ were the first to study thoroughly the release and uptake of liquids by rigid, irreversible gels of silicic acid, ferric hydroxide and aluminium hydroxide. Silicic acid hydrogel is used only to designate the harder, partially or entirely dehydrated product. Silicic acid hydrogel which is normally prepared by the destabilisation of an aqueous solution of sodium silicate has been used since long as a dehydrating agent in various processes.

The surface properties of the silicic acid hydrogel were shown to be independent of the crystalline state. Silicic acid hydrogels in various thermal treatments were studied by glc method⁸ and their changes in pore size, inner surface and structural water content worked out. An extensive review of kinetic processes involving solids has been made⁹ and reactions were classified into the categories of exothermic and endothermic types. It was shown¹⁰ that the rate of decomposition was influenced by

grain size and the attendant surface area. It was found¹¹ that the rate-constant during zeolitic dehydration followed an inverse relationship with the total water content. The activation energy was shown to be independent of particle size in aluminosilicate gel structure¹².

The present investigation reports the effect of compaction on the kinetics of thermal dehydration of two important hydroxide hydrogels.

Experimental

Silicic acid hydrogel was synthesised by cation exchange technique. After proper ageing, they were processed in accordance with the reported method¹³, in order to get rid of extraneous impurities. Aluminium hydroxide hydrogel was prepared by the interaction of $Al_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot 18H_2O$ and NH_4Cl-NH_4OH buffer at pH 9. Finally, the materials were processed with the reported method¹⁴. The kinetics of dehydration process was studied by TG method¹⁵. Pellets were prepared in hydraulic press by taking 0.5 g finely agated powder at the pressure of 1150, 1350 and 1550 kg/cm² for 1 min. No binder was used and the pellets were sufficiently strong. After fabrication, the pellets were equilibrated at $32 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The isothermal dehydration curves (not produced) showed exponential behaviour and as such first order kinetics was suggested. The method of Guggenheim¹⁶ was adopted to calculate initial water concentration (L_a) which can be dehydrated at the experimental temperature and also the rate constant K_1 for the initial stage of dehydration using equation (1).

$$\log \Delta L = \frac{-K_1 t}{2.303} + \log L_a [1 - \exp(-K_1 \Delta t)] \quad (1)$$

where ΔL is the difference between the mass loss at time $(t+\Delta t)$ and time t , the time interval Δt between the two sets of readings being kept fixed at a value greater than twice the time for 50% dehydration. Using equation (1), the rate constant was calculated from the slope of linear plots obtained by plotting $\log \Delta L$ vs t . Knowing t and having obtained K_1 from the slope, L_∞ was determined from the intercept on the log axis. Figs. 1 to 6 show the Guggenheim plots and the values of K_1 and L_∞ are recorded in Table 1. The activation energy was calculated from the usual Arrhenius plots using the rate constants (Figs. 7 and 8).

Fig. 1. Log ΔL vs time plots of silicic acid hydrogel pelletised under 1150 kg/cm^2 pressure at different temperatures: (1) 100° , (2) 130° , (3) 160° , (4) 190° .

Fig. 2. Log ΔL vs time plots of silicic acid hydrogel pelletised under 1350 kg/cm^2 pressure at different temperatures: (1) 100° , (2) 130° , (3) 160° , (4) 190° .

Fig. 3. Log ΔL vs time plots of silicic acid hydrogel pelletised under 1550 kg/cm^2 pressure at different temperatures: (1) 100° , (2) 130° , (3) 160° , (4) 190° .

Fig. 4. Log ΔL vs time plots of aluminium hydroxide hydrogel pelletised under 1150 kg/cm^2 pressure at different temperatures: (1) 100° , (2) 130° , (3) 160° , (4) 190° .

From an analysis of the above results, it has been found that at a given temperature the L_∞ values for the three different pressures ($1150\text{-}1550 \text{ kg/cm}^2$) of pelletisation, remain almost the same and this was also expected since any variation in pressure might alter the rate of dehydration but not the final loss at infinite time.

Fig. 5. Log ΔL vs time plots of aluminium hydroxide hydrogel pelletised under 1350 kg/cm² pressure at different temperatures : (1) 100°, (2) 130°, (3) 160°, (4) 190°.

Fig. 6. Log ΔL vs time plots of aluminium hydroxide hydrogel pelletised under 1550 kg/cm² pressure at different temperatures : (1) 100°, (2) 130°, (3) 160°, (4) 190°.

The rate constants of dehydration for both of silicic acid and aluminium hydroxide hydrogel, were found to be reduced on application of pressure which might be due to the back pressure set up by water vapour in the pores. In the study of pressure-effect the reaction rate constants were calculated only for the initial stage of dehydration. In the pressurised condition, the rate of dehydration decreased in comparison to that of loose grains.

No significant pressure effect was observed with respect to the $(K_p)_1$ values in the range studied in

Fig. 7. Arrhenius plots of pellets of silicic acid hydrogel compacted under different pressure for the initial stage of dehydration : (1) 1150, (2) 1350, (3) 1550 kg/cm².

Fig. 8. Arrhenius plots of pellets of aluminium hydroxide hydrogel compacted under different pressure for the initial stage of dehydration : (1) 1150, (2) 1350, (3) 1550 kg/cm².

the present investigation which might be due to the fact that no overall compaction, particle disintegration or orientation occurred. Thus it appears that there might be a critical pressure upto which reaction rate may decrease (not studied here) but beyond that point the change was not very significant.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANTS $(Kp)_1$ AND L_{∞} AS DETERMINED FROM $\log \Delta L$ vs TIME PLOTS AT DIFFERENT PRESSURES AT THE INITIAL STAGE OF DEHYDRATION

Hydrogel	Temp. °C	Pressure of pelletisation kg/cm^2	$(Kp)_1/\text{min}$	L_{∞} g
Silicic acid	100	1150	0.0690	0.1142
		1350	0.0678	0.1156
		1550	0.0636	0.1146
Silicic acid	130	1150	0.1398	0.1238
		1350	0.1388	0.1232
		1550	0.1390	0.1230
Silicic acid	160	1150	0.1892	0.1252
		1350	0.1886	0.1255
		1550	0.1842	0.1260
Silicic acid	190	1150	0.4062	0.1264
		1350	0.3998	0.1260
		1550	0.4030	0.1278
Aluminium hydroxide	100	1150	0.0806	0.0340
		1350	0.0751	0.0332
		1550	0.0721	0.0336
Aluminium hydroxide	130	1150	0.1290	0.0448
		1350	0.1092	0.0520
		1550	0.1004	0.0526
Aluminium hydroxide	160	1150	0.1578	0.0560
		1350	0.1382	0.0580
		1550	0.1374	0.0575
Aluminium hydroxide	190	1150	0.1890	0.0595
		1350	0.1886	0.0586
		1550	0.1879	0.0590

From the extent of linearity of $\log [(L_{\infty}-L)/L_{\infty}]$ vs time plots (Figs. 9-12), the validity of first order law was examined with respect to variation of pressure and the results are given in Table 2.

Fig. 9. Isothermal dehydration curve for silicic acid hydrogel pelletised under 1150 kg/cm^2 pressure at different temperatures.

Fig. 10. Isothermal dehydration curves of silicic acid hydrogel pelletised under different pressures.

Fig. 11. Isothermal dehydration curves for aluminium hydroxide hydrogel pelletised under different pressures at different temperatures.

Fig. 12. Isothermal dehydration curves for aluminum hydroxide hydrogel pelletised under 1550 kg/cm² pressure at different temperatures.

TABLE 2—EXTENT OF VALIDITY OF FIRST ORDER LAW AS DETERMINED FROM log [(L_∞ - L)/L_∞] vs TIME PLOTS

Hydrogel	Temp. °C	Pressure of pelletisation kg/cm ²	First order valid upto % dehydration
Silicic acid	100	1150	41.16
		1350	39.74
		1550	32.39
Silicic acid	130	1150	52.14
		1350	49.88
		1550	48.71
Silicic acid	160	1150	66.21
		1350	56.35
		1550	52.02
Silicic acid	190	1150	69.80
		1350	65.93
		1550	61.10
Aluminium hydroxide	100	1150	48.72
		1350	47.52
		1550	45.05
Aluminium hydroxide	130	1150	61.19
		1350	60.09
		1550	58.82
Aluminium hydroxide	160	1150	67.56
		1350	66.89
		1550	66.38
Aluminium hydroxide	190	1150	71.16
		1350	69.80
		1550	69.10

Effect of pressure was noticed in the validity of the first order kinetics which was inversely affected by the increase of pressure. This might be due to the fact that under pressurised condition the escape of water is retarded through the compact mass containing decomposed materials whose surfaces were still hydrophilic in nature. The calculated values of activation energy from Arrhenius plot have been represented in Table 3 and Figs. 7 and 8.

In each case activation energy increased and showed a positive proportionality with the pressure of pelletisation. The escape of loosely bound water

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION ENERGIES AS DETERMINED FROM ARRHENIUS PLOTS AT THE INITIAL STAGE OF DEHYDRATION OF HYDROXIDE HYDROGEL FORMED AT DIFFERENT PRESSURE

Hydrogel	Pressure of pelletisation kg/cm ²	Activation energies (E _p), cal mol ⁻¹
Silicic acid	1150	6.64
	1350	6.86
	1550	7.32
Aluminium hydroxide	1150	8.75
	1350	8.89
	1550	4.12

was a low energy process as evidenced from the values of activation energy and as such the variation with respect to pressure was fairly significant. Although under pressurised condition there is possibility of particle disintegration along with formation of channels yet no such effect was noticed within the pressure range as studied in the present investigation.

Conclusion : (i) Positive effect of pressure was noticed in the validity of the first order kinetics which was inversely affected by the increase of pressure.

(ii) Rate constants of the initial stage of dehydration decreased in comparison to that of loose grains which might be due to the back pressure set up by the water vapour inside the pore.

(iii) Under pressurised condition only the exposed surface area was diminished. But because of the highly porous hydrogel, no positive extra diffusion barrier was created due to compaction and as such the pressure effect was not very significant.

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